

Draft Programe

”STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION IN THE CONTEXT OF SECURITY AND DEFENCE ”

24-26.09.2024 – HOTEL SHERATON, BUCHAREST

5-7 Dorobanților Way, district 1

Platinum Conference Room

Date/Time Bucharest (EET / GMT+3)	Intervention/Panel	Speakers
Day 1 - Tuesday, 24/09/2024		
08.30-09.30	<i>Registration</i>	
09.30-10.15	Opening Speeches	<p>General Liviu Uzlău, Commander/Rector, ”Alexandru Ioan Cuza” Police Academy</p> <p>Police Quaestor, Associate Prof. Cătălin Andruș, Director of the National College of Home Affairs (CNAI) & course co-director</p> <p>Professor Alina Bârgăoanu, PhD, Dean, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (SNSPA) - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director</p> <p>Dr. Kieran Doyle, National University of Ireland, Maynooth & course co-director</p> <p>Ana Tinca, State Secretary, Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p> <p>Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
10.15-10.45	<i>Official group photo/Coffee break</i>	
10.45-11.00	Presentations of CNAI and ESDC	<p>Police Quaestor Conf.univ.dr. Cătălin Andruș, director CNAI & course co-director</p> <p>Moritz Herzberg, Training Manager ESDC</p>
11.00-12.30	Communicating CSDP in the context of Euro-Atlantic evolutions	<p>Prof.dr. Iulian Chifu – President of the Conflict Prevention and Early Warning Center Bucharest</p> <p>The former Counselor for Strategic Affairs and International Security of the Romanian President and counselor state of prime minister</p> <p>Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
12.30-13.30	<i>Lunch break</i> – Avalon restaurant, Hotel Sheraton	
13.30-14.45	Strategic communication and hybrid treats	<p>Professor Bernard Siman, PhD – EGMONT Institute</p> <p>Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>
14.45-15.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.00-16.15	StratCom Concepts (Communication effects, narrative analysis and development, the role of mass media in the implementation of StratCom priorities)	<p>Associate Prof. Flavia Durach, PhD, SNSPA</p> <p>Flavia Voinea, Manager, Radio Romania</p> <p>Claudia Nicolae, General Manager, Agerpres</p> <p>Moderator: Asist.univ.dr. Roberta Răducu - SNSPA</p>
16.15-17.00	Leadership and Decision-Making	<p>Simulation. Exercises – Team dynamics.</p> <p>Intro to team assignments</p>

		Facilitator : Associated Prof. Flavia Durach , PhD, SNSPA
17.00-17.30	Tour de table	Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
18.30-21.00	<i>Welcome cocktail</i> Hosted by National College of Home Affairs <i>Location: Hotel Sheraton</i>	
Day 2 – Wednesday, 25/09/2024		
09.00-10.30	The strategic approach of STRATCOM in MFA	Andrei ȚĂRNEA – Director general of the Communication and Public Diplomacy Department, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.30	Crisis Management and Crisis Communication	Dr. Raed Arafat , State Secretary, Ministry of Internal Affairs, Romania Conf. univ. dr. Monica Bîră , SNSPA Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
12.30-13.30	<i>Lunch break</i> – Avalon restaurant, Hotel Sheraton	
13.30-15.00	Disinformation, Fake News, Propaganda (Strategic narratives as resilience-building instruments against disinformation) StratCom and intelligence approach	Prof. univ. dr. Alina Bârgăoanu , professor and dean, SNSPA - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director Remus Ștefureac , STRATEGIC Thinking Group / INSCOP Research Prof. univ. dr. Miruna Butnaru-Troncotă , SNSPA Moderator: Asist. univ. dr. Florin Zeru - SNSPA
15.00-15.15	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.15-16.30	Communicating the EU: CSDP Missions and Operations – Communicating through Dialogue	Dr. Kieran Doyle , National University of Ireland, Maynooth & course co-director Răzvan Budeanu , Expert FRONTEX Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
16.30-17.30	Leadership and Decision-Making	Team assignments Facilitator: Drd. Marina Enache , SNSPA
18.30-21.00	Romanian Painting Exhibition / UNESCO Cultural Center Mihai Eminescu <i>Official Dinner</i> Hosted by National College of Home Affairs <i>Location: Hotel Sheraton</i>	
Day 3 – Thursday, 26/09/2024		
09.00-10.30	Strategic communication in the new digital ecosystem. The Role of Dealing with Cybersecurity and Hybrid Threats	Dan Cimpean – Romanian National Cyber Security Directorate, Professor Bernard Siman , PhD – EGMONT institute Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI

10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.00-12.30	EU Policies on StratCom/ EEAS structures on StratCom (Crisis tackling it from the policy side)	Dr. Kieran Doyle , National University of Ireland, Maynooth & course co-director Dr. Simion Costea , PhD, the former project manager DG Near Neighborhood and Enlargement Negotiations / European Commission Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , CNAI
12.30-13.30	<i>Lunch break – Avalon restaurant, Hotel Sheraton</i>	
13.30-15.00	StratCom Fundamentals (Persuasion, campaign planning and implementation. Conflict analysis and dialogue) StratCom – EU vs NATO Approach	Major Roxana Davidovits , Head of the Online Communication Department, Ministry of National Defence Conf.univ.dr. Loredana Vladu , SNSPA Gen (r) Liviu Dănilă , CNAI Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI
15.00-15.15	<i>Coffee break</i>	
15.15-16.30	RECAP Panel Syndicates	Facilitator: Asist.univ.dr. Cătălina Nastasiu , SNSPA
16.30-17.15	Admin remarks, survey, Handling of Certificates	Police Quaestor Conf.univ.dr. Cătălin Andruș , director of the National College of Home Affairs & course co-director Prof. univ. dr. Alina Bârgăoanu , professor and dean, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration - College of Communication and Public Relations & course co-director Moritz Herzberg , Training Manager ESDC Moderator: dr. Bogdan Marinescu , National College of Home Affairs
18.00-19.00	Departure of participants	